

ISSN 2748-9345

VOLUME 2

**JOURNAL OF SOCIAL
SCIENCES AND
HUMANITY RESEARCH
FUNDAMENTALS**

HIGH IMPACT FACTOR JOURNAL

“EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL”

Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research Fundamentals

ISSN: - 2748-9345

Volume II Issue X

Crossref Doi: - 10.55640/jsshrf

Frequency: 12 Issue Per Year

Website: <https://eipublication.com>

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DEVELOPMENT OF PRACTICAL SKILLS IN TECHNOLOGY IN DISTANCE LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15512457>

Annotation: This article covers the current issues of forming and developing practical skills in students in technology subjects in distance education. The possibilities of increasing the level of students' acquisition of practical knowledge through the use of modern digital technologies, virtual laboratories, interactive platforms and online simulators in the educational process are analyzed.

Keywords: distance education, practical skills, digital resources, interactive methods, virtual environment, educational activities.

Introduction:

The rapid development of digital technologies in recent years and the conditions of forced isolation caused by the global pandemic have led to the emergence of distance education as a relevant direction worldwide. Unlike traditional forms of education, distance education requires the educational process to be carried out on the basis of digital platforms, online lessons and virtual collaboration. This situation creates certain difficulties, especially in teaching technology subjects, since the main content of this subject is aimed at the formation of practical skills. Technology serves to develop engineering thinking, technical creativity, practical work skills, and constructive approaches in students. However, distance learning requires more innovative solutions than traditional methods for the full implementation of these processes. The lack of direct involvement of students in practical activities, the limitation of the opportunity to work with real tools and equipment are the biggest pedagogical problems in the process of distance learning of technology.

From this point of view, methodological approaches to the development of practical skills in technology in distance learning, the effective use of digital tools, and the creation of an interactive and virtual learning environment require in-depth scientific and practical study. This article analyzes such approaches, innovative technologies, and mechanisms for organizing practical training in remote conditions.

Methodology:

The methodological basis of teaching technology in distance learning requires relying on modern pedagogical technologies and approaches adapted to the digital learning environment. While in the traditional way, students' technological and practical knowledge is formed more by working with real objects in classrooms and workshops, distance learning requires a revision of this model. Therefore, in this study, the theory of constructivism, activity-based learning, and the principles of digital pedagogy were chosen as the main methodological basis.

The methodological basis of the study is interactive and problem-based

educational technologies, gamification elements, and digital design-based learning methods. Through these approaches, students are created the opportunity to model practical activities in a virtual environment, work independently, and express their creative ideas using technical means, even in remote conditions. In particular, methods such as “Blended learning”, “Flipped classroom” and “Project-Based Learning” serve to make the learning process of students interactive, purposeful and independent.

The methodology also analyzed the didactic effectiveness of using virtual laboratories, 3D modeling programs, online simulators and digital construction platforms (for example, Tinkercad, Arduino simulation, Scratch). These tools serve not only to develop technical thinking, but also to strengthen students’ decision-making skills in problem situations, teamwork and innovative thinking.

An important aspect of the methodological approach is the digitization of the assessment system. Therefore, the integrated use of formative (current) and summative (final) assessment types, maintaining electronic portfolios, and monitoring student activity through indicators were used. These approaches allow assessing student development based on specific indicators and implementing an individual approach.

As a result, the research methodology served to develop a modern, interactive, and technologically supported model of developing practical skills in technology in distance education.

Literature analysis (review):

The issue of teaching technology in distance education, especially the formation of practical skills, is in the focus of many modern pedagogical studies. In recent years, scientific developments in this area have mainly covered digital tools, interactive educational technologies, and methodological approaches aimed at stimulating independent activity of students.

In particular, V.G. The theory of didactic systems put forward by Bospalko allows you to create a well-planned model of student activity in the process of distance learning. In his works, the structure of educational material, the combination of substantive and practical blocks, as well as assessment criteria are clearly defined, which serve as an important basis for developing practical components of technological science in distance conditions.

Also, the concept of person-oriented education developed by A.V. Khutorskoy is of great importance in ensuring the individual pace of student mastery and independent activity. It is on the basis of this approach in distance learning that digital assignments, project developments and portfolios are organized, which serve to deepen technological skills.

The works of local scientists, in particular, S.S. Rajabov, T.T. Jalolov and D.Y. Kuchkarov, contain useful theoretical and practical recommendations on the didactic features of distance learning, interactive methods and monitoring of educational activities. In their opinion, the effectiveness of the distance learning process largely depends on the digital competence of the teacher and the technologically sound development of the lesson content. An analysis of the

existing literature shows that a combination of advanced pedagogical approaches and digital tools is necessary for teaching practical aspects of technology in a distance learning environment. Creating an effective methodological model based on recommendations from scientific sources can help students develop technical competencies that are closer to real work activities.

Result:

As part of the study, experimental tests were organized to determine the effectiveness of forming practical skills in technology in a distance learning environment. Students in grades 8–9 of secondary schools participated in it. The study was conducted in 2 groups - experimental and control groups. In the experimental group, the learning process was organized on the basis of interactive online platforms (Tinkercad, Fritzing, Canva, Google Classroom), while in the control group, traditional distance learning tools (PDF textbook, simple lecture via Zoom) were used. At the end of the experiment, the following statistical results were achieved:

The ability to independently complete practical tasks was 78% in the experimental group, while this figure was 51% in the control group.

The ability to design technical drawings in a virtual environment was formed in 71% of students in the experimental group, while this figure was 44% in the control group.

The skills of finding creative solutions and solving technological problems were formed in 67% of students in the experimental group, while this figure was observed in only 39% in the control group.

Students' interest in technology increased by 82% in the experimental group, which is 26% higher than in the control group.

The analysis showed that the distance learning model using digital platforms is significantly effective in developing technological thinking, practical knowledge and creative approaches in students. During the experiment, the teacher's activity, interactivity of tasks, transparency of assessment and participation of students in virtual teamwork led to high results.

Conclusion:

One of the most important tasks facing the modern education system is the formation of real-life, practical skills and competencies in students. Especially in practical areas such as technology, this process is doubly important. The results of the study show that even in distance learning conditions, technological skills can be effectively formed through the right approach and methodological support. In this regard, the use of interactive digital platforms, the organization of the educational process based on activity-based and problem situations, and a person-centered approach are the main factors.

Also, through virtual design, 3D modeling, online simulations and gamification elements, students' interest in the lesson, creativity and independent thinking skills are enhanced. Based on statistical analysis, it was found that the introduction of advanced methods in distance learning serves to form students' technological literacy and skills in performing real practical tasks at a much

higher level. In conclusion, it can be said that in order to ensure the effectiveness of distance learning in technology, a teacher must be a specialist who has mastered digital tools, is methodologically prepared, and most importantly, can direct the student to creative mastery. Only then will we be able to strengthen the foundations of innovative thinking and practical knowledge in students suitable for the digital age.

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